

NIGERIAN-SOUTH AFRICA INTERVENTIONS ON WILDLIFE CONSERVATION IN HOST COMMUNITIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Wildlife conservation to enhance tourism development has been a herculean task for most countries in sub-Sahara Africa largely due to funding, and international support programmes. In Nigeria, these requirements constitute challenges for the country towards the sustainable tourism development for the country economic transformation. Apparently, this has made Nigeria which is one of the emerging economies to seek for intervention from one of the BRICS member-South African to enhance wildlife conservation in host communities in Nigeria. The paper examined the level of awareness of wildlife practices among host communities in Nigeria, and, investigates challenges facing support zones programmes aim at Wildlife conservation in host communities. It also, examined the institutional interventions between Nigerian and South Africa on wildlife conservation towards tourism development in Nigeria. The paper is centered on descriptive research design which relied on primary and secondary data. The study concluded that there is apt need for sustainable collaboration between Nigeria and South Africa towards capacity building and knowledge sharing on wildlife conservation, which will be of immense contributions to tourism development in Africa.*

Introduction

Tourism is the world's largest growing industry with no signs of slowing down in the years ahead and is an important economic industry in the world. Tourism activities accounted for US\$7.6

trillion or 10.2% of total global gross domestic product (GDP), and 292 million jobs representing one out of every ten jobs in 2017. Tourism exports during the same period were estimated to be more than US\$1.5trillion while

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international tourist arrivals is over 1.2 billion (World Economic Forum, 2017). Wildlife represents biodiversity, essential for our health and the well-being of the whole planet. We live in an interconnected ecological system, where each macro- and microorganism, whether animal, plant or fish affects the other (Mathew, Gantait & Swamy, 2017). In the same vein, literature revealed that wildlife viewing, and other related ecotourism are the key drivers of tourist visit to Africa. According to the UNWTO Report 'Towards Measuring the Economic Value of Wildlife Watching Tourism in Africa,' indicated that 7% of world tourism relates to wildlife tourism grows at about 3%, annually. The same document shows that a total of 14 countries in Africa are generating an estimated US\$ 142 million in entrance fees for protected areas (UNWTO, 2015).

Consequently, Alteration of the natural habitat of any organism will trigger a dynamo effect, so non-equilibrium in the ecological system as a whole endangers the life cycle of many species. Wildlife remains a major concern for the international, regional and local communities. Among the multiple risks that menace wildlife are: diseases, climate change and actions of human nature, such as poaching and illegal trafficking (Atuo, Connell, Agida & Agaldo, 2020; Ntuli, Jagers, Linell, Sjöstedt & Muchapondwa, 2019; Bello, Lovelock & Carr , 2017). Similarly, Community-Based Conservation (CBC) is a strategy used throughout the world to save wildlife, which has

its modern roots in the experience of conservationists working in poorer countries during the 1960s and 1970s. Conservationists came to realize that local people, who commonly are hostile to wildlife conservation, had to be won over as supporters of their efforts (World Conservation Union 1980; Parker, 1982; Hackel, 1999); they saw that without the cooperation of rural people, wildlife conservation efforts would be doomed. This is certainly true in Nigeria, where rural inhabitants often view wildlife conservation as misguided because it puts the needs of wildlife above those of people (Shrestha & Lapeyre, 2018).

Wildlife conservation to enhance tourism development has been a herculean task for most countries in sub-Sahara Africa largely due to funding, and international support programmes. In Nigeria, these requirements constitute challenges for the country towards the sustainable tourism development for the country economic transformation. Despite the significant contribution of CBC scheme to wildlife conservation in developed world and other developing nations such as Kenya, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, and South Africa among others, the approach failed to reduce poaching activities and illegal lumbering of natural resources in Old Oyo National Park (OONP) Nigeria. A recent study by Coker, Ajayi and Dada (2020) on knowledge of Nigeria wildlife conservation law in OONP indicates that despite the awareness of conservation law among the locals, there is still heavy poaching and violation of conservation law

at the parks. In the same vein, Tijani (2007) argued that increase in population of large mammals in OONP has largely been associated with increased enforcement efforts and not provision of incentives, the locals were not genuinely supporting the project. The failure of SZCP according to him is as a result of various face-off emanating from community desire to meet their various needs and aspiration such as needs to provide pasture for animal, lumbering, poaching amongst others (Tijani, 2007). Apparently, this has made Nigeria which is one of the emerging economies to seek for intervention from one of the BRICS member-South African to enhance wildlife conservation in host communities in Nigeria.

Goal 15 of the United Nation Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) aims to protect, restore, and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss. From the foregoing, it is clear, that this goal 15 and its various targets are of utmost relevance to the problem of wildlife conservation and its management in the study areas and by extension the Nigeria protected areas, reserve zones and national parks at large. In other words, despite huge investment on wildlife conservation in Nigeria, there is laxity in government policy towards wildlife conservation as a pathway for tourism development. Against this background, research of this magnitude to examine the Nigerian-South Africa interventions on wildlife

Conservation in host communities in Nigeria is considered timely.

Wildlife Practices among Host communities in Nigeria: Level of Awareness

Adeyemi and Taofeek 2020 as reported in Reddy and Ugle (2008) argued that sustainable management techniques are required to maintain and conserve biodiversity. The study further added that conservation can only be achieved through accurate information about the status and distribution of biodiversity, which serves as the foundation for other life forms (Adeyemi & Taofeek, 2020). In the same vein, Ogunjinmi and Braimoh (2018) conducted a study on the assessment of community awareness and participation in ecotourism in Old Oyo National Park, Nigeria. The study assessed the level of community awareness and participation in ecotourism in Old Oyo National Park, Nigeria. The research found out that 48% of the respondents were aware of ecotourism and 46% participated in ecotourism. The study showed that there exists a relationship between ecotourism awareness and participation. The study affirmed that awareness, active involvement of communities in stakeholder meetings, decision-making and provision of start-up capital are important for ecotourism development in the park.

Similarly, Osunsina and Fagbeyiro (2015) in their study examine the local community perception and attitude towards the non-utilization of natural resources in Old-Oyo

National Park, Oyo State, Nigeria. The study was conducted in Old Oyo National Park, Oyo State to assess the local community perception and reaction to the non-utilization of natural resources. Primary data were collected from five (5) local communities in support zone of Old Oyo National Park. The result shows that some of the respondents (41.5 %) agreed that the rules and regulations of the park were strict. Majority of the respondents strongly disagreed to the non-utilization of natural resources in Old Oyo National Park. By restricting access to these park resources, the people feel denied and as such majority (54.3 %) of the respondents are non-compliant to the rules and regulations of the park. The study concludes with an advocacy to integrate local people in the decision making of the park.

Sam, Nnaji and Etefia (2014) explored the level of community participation in the conservation of natural resources in Akamkpa Local Government Area, Southern Cross River State, Nigeria. The study aimed at establishing the extent of community participation in natural resources conservation in the study area. Findings revealed that, the level of participation significantly influences forest resources conservation, and that community involvement has a significant influence on wildlife conservation. In a study conducted by Coker, Ajayi and Dada (2020) which critically examined the knowledge of Nigeria wildlife conservation laws among officials of Okomu and Old Oyo National Parks, Nigeria. The two parks had a

total of 431 staff consisting of 281 in OONP and 150 in ONP as of September 2018, simple random sampling was used to administer structured questionnaire to 50 ONP and 130 OONP staff. The study indicates that 95.6 % and 96.7 % of respondents in both parks have heard of wildlife laws and affirmed the existence of wildlife laws in Nigeria respectively. The study concluded that Park officials of Okomu and Old Oyo National Parks were not adequately familiar with Nigerian wildlife conservation laws.

Wildlife Conservation in Host Communities: Challenges Facing Support Zones Programmes

According to Olaleru and Egonmwan (2014) that explores wildlife conservation challenges in Okomu national park, Nigeria. The study looked at the challenges of conserving the park's wildlife and other resources. A combination of primary and secondary data was used for the research. Finding reveal that farming had the highest value of record of offences followed by hunting and logging, entry, and collection of non-timber products. The study concluded that people encroached into the Okomu national park for farming, hunting (poaching), logging and collection of non-timber products despite the illegality of the actions. Thus, community people saw wildlife as nature's gift that could be used for subsistence and commercial purposes, hence, conservation of resources in the park could be enhanced if government laws on protection of the areas are enforced.

According to Ajayi and Ayodele (2018) that evaluated the benefits and challenges of living near a protected area in Nigeria; the case of Okomu National Park. The study assessed the benefits and challenges that accompanied living near Okomu National Park, Nigeria. Result reveals that Majority of the respondents (85 %) indicated that they have benefited nothing by living near the park. (99.2 %) of the respondents of the adjoining communities were aware of the existence of the National Park and (77.4 %) of the respondents indicated that locals were not involved in Park management. The study identified some of the challenges of people living near the park which include inaccessibility to bush meat, inaccessibility to land for farming and wildlife disturbance.

Similarly, Ijeoma and Ogbara (2013) examined the challenges of wildlife management in Kainji Lake National Park, Nigeria. The study assessed challenges of wildlife management in Kainji Lake National Park, Nigeria in order to determine the constraints to effective management. Findings revealed that the major causes of conflict in KLNP are hunting (95.4 %), illegal grazing of cattle (95.4 %), fishing (85.11 %) and collection of non-timber forest product (71.96 %). Insufficient infrastructure (94.34 %) and inadequate maintenance of equipment (94.34 %) were ranked the most pressing challenges of staff respondents in KLNP. The consequences of these challenges include insecurity in the park (73.58%), reduction in management practices (62.26 %) and inefficiency (28.30 %).

In a study conducted by Anwadike (2020) that evaluates the biodiversity conservation in Nigeria: perception, challenges, and possible remedies. The study essentially seeks to highlight some of the unwholesome practices that endanger biodiversity and to sensitize the populace on the importance of biodiversity conservation practices in Nigeria. The study identified some major threats to biodiversity conservation in Nigeria include poverty, economic development, incomplete or non-implementation and non-ratification by government of international treaties and conventions on conservation issues, ambiguous governmental laws on biodiversity, climate change, pollution, amongst others.

According to Audu and Ayuba (2016) that evaluated the biodiversity conservation in Nigeria: contemporary challenges for ecologist. The study discusses biodiversity and its significance and looked at the status of Nigeria's biodiversity and why it is important to conserve it. The study relied on secondary sources of data collection. The study identifies poverty, population growth, deforestation and habitat degradation among several other factors that contribute to biodiversity loss in Nigeria. The study acknowledged that the methods of biodiversity conservation in Nigeria shows that protected area system is the main method of biodiversity conservation, although in some cases it is been supported by community-based conservation approach. The study concluded that Priorities for ecologist thus include

understanding the causal relationships between people and biodiversity, placing economic value on biodiversity and prioritizing target outcomes and indicators.

According to Ogogo, Nchor and Jacob (2010) that investigated the challenges of buffer zone management in Cross River National Park, Southeastern Nigeria. The study assessed the challenges of buffer zone management in some (adjacent) support zone communities in Oban Division of Cross River National Park, Nigeria. Study reveals that (68.68%) of the respondents proved they were not aware of the existence of the buffer zone and the policies governing it. A small segment of the community (11.21%) accepted that the programme has tremendous enhanced their economic status while a very small proportion of the study population (23.28%) were reported for involvement buffer zone management. The study concluded that a large percentage of the members of the surrounding communities claimed ignorance of the existence of the buffer zone and the laws establishing it and recommended for an aggressive public enlightenment campaign programme to fully educate the people on the park's conservation projects.

Nigerian-South Africa Wildlife Conservation and Tourism Development in Nigeria: Institutional Interventions

According to Adewumi, Edward, Agunbiade and Oyeniran (2018) that examines the Nigerian wildlife management policy, institutional and legal framework. The study assessed in holistic

the various policies and institutional legal framework by government geared towards wildlife management in Nigerian. The study is purely based on secondary sources of data collection. It reviewed articles on Federal Environmental Protection Agency act (FEPA), National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency Establishment) Act, 2007 (NESREA), Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), Wildlife Conservation Society Nigeria Program Conservation Strategy. The study emphasized that the existing variety of legislation on biodiversity needs coordination for effective application mechanism on the conservation of wildlife for sustainable uses for tourism, parks, and efficient management of the forest for production of goods and services throughout the country.

Similarly, Sotolu, Tyowua and Akanbi (2016) assessed the impact of wildlife policy on management of wildlife resources in Cross River National Park, Nigeria. The study evaluated how policy affects management of wildlife resources in Cross River National Park (CRNP). Data were collected through two sets of structured questionnaires were administered to Park Managers (PMs) and support zone communities (SZCs). Result indicated that 68.8 % of the park managers at both divisions acknowledged the existence of other forms of land uses within which are anti-conservation. The result added that the host communities consider the national act as being harmful (50.6 %), on the other hand

(26.6 %) of park manager consider this policy as being adequately effective, some (20.3) decide that it is moderately effective, while others are of the opinion that it is mildly effective (26.6 %) or not effective (26.6 %). The study conclude that the act is a blueprint, while its implementation is the real task; it submitted that legal parameters need to be employed in maintaining checks and balances, are expected to be flexible enough to accommodate unpredictable and unstable human nature. It advocated that park communities should developed, and their social status elevated by providing better sources of livelihood to them.

Furthermore, Ijaiya and Joseph (2014) examined the needs to rethinking environmental law enforcement in Nigeria. The study investigated the use of environmental laws by different enforcement agencies in Nigeria, the methods of enforcement these agencies invoke, and the challenges they face in enforcing the relevant laws the study found out that most of the environmental problems in Nigeria are because of the lackadaisical attitude of government towards the enforcement of environmental laws. The environmental laws lacked adequate policies for coordinating the environmental laws and making them effective, and there were also no mechanisms for collection and management of environmental statistics. The study identified environmental sanitation and not eradication of environmental pollution, desertification, deforestation, and use of pesticides and other

core environmental problems as major concern of the government.

Methodology

This study employed descriptive research design. The study was carried out in Old Oyo National Park. Oyo State Nigeria. The sample were selected from the existing National Park in Nigeria due to her history and increasing challenges of poaching of wildlife animals. Primary and secondary data sources were used. Secondary data were sourced from related journal encyclopedia, books, and internet. The study population for this research is 65,320 comprised of the entire residents in the 120 adjoining communities, villages and settlements that surround the parks which fall within 0-10km in the Old-Oyo National Parks. Taro Yamane Formula Sample Size Determination was used to determine the sample size. Therefore, a total of 398 copies of questionnaire were administered on the respondents. Afterwards the adjoining communities around the National Park were grouped into six ranges. In addition, systematic sampling techniques were used to select 10 communities in each of the ranges totaling 60 communities. In each of the community, questionnaires were distributed to the respondents (farmers, community leaders and hunters), through stratified sampling techniques disproportionately, totaling 398 respondents. The respondents were selected based on gender, occupation, and experience on wildlife conservation in Nigeria. Data were analyzed

through descriptive analysis. Ethical considerations were considered during and after the study. Verbal consents were obtained from the respondents, and also confidentiality and anonymity were considered in the study.

Findings and Discussion of Findings

Table 1 shows the respondents' level of awareness on the conservation rules and regulation. The result showed that larger percentage of the respondents from Oyo-Ile range 25(62.5%) Sepeteri range 57(64.0%) and Yemoso range 38(53.5%) indicated yes which implies that they have high level of awareness on any conservation rules and regulation while more than half respondents from Tede range 58(53.7 %), Marguba range 22(55.0 %) and Tesi range 21(53.8 %) indicated No which implies that the participants has a low of level of awareness on any conservation rules and regulation.

Out of the respondents who indicated yes that they were aware of the wildlife conservation laws, policy and regulation of National Park, majority of the participants from Tede range 27(54.0 %), Oyo-Ile range 14(56.0 %) and Marguba range 8(44.4 %) indicated that they got to know about wildlife conservation laws, policy and regulation of National Park through the Public awareness by park management which implies that awareness were intensively carried out by the park management in some of the ranges of the Old Oyo national park. In the same vein, 25(43.9 %) of the respondents from Sepeteri range reported that they got to know about wildlife conservation laws, policy and

regulation through their Neighbour & friend also majority of the participants from Yemoso range 13(34.2 %) got to know about wildlife conservation laws, policy and regulation through their community leaders while majority of the respondents from Tesi range got to know about wildlife conservation laws, policy and regulation through radio and television. This is similar to Oladeji and Fatukasi (2017) on a study participatory approach to conservation and management of protected area in Nigeria: case study of Osse River Park project where majority of the respondents got to know about the park through the media.

Findings also reveal that more than one third of the respondents from all the six range in the study area indicated that the National Park rule help in preservation and conservation of wildlife in the park. This is supported by a study carried out by Ogunjinmi, and Braimoh (2018) researched on the assessment of community awareness and participation in ecotourism in Old Oyo National Park, Nigeria where 48% of the respondents were aware of ecotourism.

Furthermore, table 1 shows majority of the respondents from Tede range 37(74.0 %), Oyo-Ile range 21(84.0 %), Sepeteri range 43(75.4 %) and Tesi range 12(66.7 %) reported that the wildlife conservation policy affects their live hood while Marguba range 8(44.4 %) and Yemoso range 22(57.9 %) indicated that the wildlife conservation policy did not affect their live hood in any way. The result support Toyobo, Raheem, and Oyeleye (2014)

investigated conservation strategies of wildlife resources in the Old Oyo National Park, Nigeria, in which the result shows that considerable degree of effectiveness of the strategies employed by the authority of the park, as majority of the respondents are aware of the status of the park as a protected area.

However out of the respondents of about 137(35.3 %) who indicated that the wildlife conservation policy affect their livelihood many of them from Tede range 27(67.6 %), Oyo-Ile range 11(52.4 %), Marguba range 4(50.0 %) and Yemoso range 8(50.0 %) indicated Insufficient land for farming as one of the way the rules and regulation of the conservation affect their life hood while Sepeteri range 22(51.2 %) and Tesi range 7(58.3 %) indicated Prohibition on illegal poaching of as one of the way the rules and regulation of the conservation affect their life hood. Also, the result on table 1 shows that majority of about 253(65.2 %) of the respondents from all the six ranges in the study area reported that they never intrude into the protected.

Also, table 2 show the findings of the joint effect of the independent variables of awareness on the existence of national park in this communities [$\beta=0.577$, $t=2.552$ and $p=0.012$], awareness on

conservation effort being made to protect wildlife [$\beta = 0.470$, $t=2.657$ and $p=0.008$], awareness on any government policy or law for wildlife conservation in the national park [$\beta = 0.620$, $t=3.034$ and ($p=0.003$)], and awareness on any guideline or rules given by NPSON on how to conserve wildlife as influence or effect on the host communities [$\beta = -0.462$, $t=-2.077$ and $p=0.038$] had significant effect on the host communities at 0.05 level of significance since the p-value was less than 0.05 we therefore reject null hypothesis. Similarly, the result conforms to Nyataya (2019) that explored community-based organizations in environment conservation endeavors in Rwanda. Findings of the study indicate that respondents have a clear knowledge and understanding on environmental conservation and role played by CBOs in general and SACOLA towards the efforts directed to environment protection and conservation; majority (38.03%) of the respondents were noted to have been members of the association for a period between 6 and 10 years. SACOLA conducted mobilization activities, sensitization, training and educating communities in the selected study area and its environs on the importance of environment conservation.

Table 1: Awareness of Wildlife Conservation

Variable	Tede Range (n=108)	Oyo-Ile Range (n=40)	Sepete ri Range (n=89)	Margu ba Range (n=40)	Yemes o Range (n=71)	Tesi Range (n=40)
	F(%)	F(%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)	F (%)
Are you aware of any conservation rules and regulation						
Yes	50(46.3)	25(62.5)	57(64.0)	18(45.0)	38(53.5)	18(45.0)
No	58(53.7)	15(37.5)	32(36.0)	22(55.0)	33(46.5)	21(52.5)
How did you get to know about wildlife conservation laws, policy and regulation						
Public awareness by park management	27(54.0)	14(56.0)	10(17.5)	8(44.4)	10(26.3)	3(16.7)
Neighbour & friend	9(18.0)	4(16.0)	25(43.9)	3(16.7)	9(23.7)	5(27.8)
Television & radio	6(12.0)	2(8.0)	11(19.3)	3(16.7)	6(15.8)	6(33.3)
Community head	8(16.0)	5(20.0)	11(19.3)	4(22.2)	13(34.2)	4(22.2)
Did the rule help in preservation and conservation of wildlife in the park						
True	43(86.0)	18(72.0)	34(59.6)	16(88.9)	33(86.8)	17(94.4)
False	7(14.0)	7(28.0)	23(40.4)	2(11.1)	5(13.2)	1(5.6)
Did the wildlife conservation policy affect your live hood						
Yes	37(74.0)	21(84.0)	43(75.4)	8(44.4)	16(42.1)	12(66.7)

No	13(13.0)	4(16.0)	14(24.6)	10(55.6)	22(57.9)	6(33.3)
In what area did rules and regulation affect you						
Insufficient land for farming	27(67.6)	11(52.4)	14(32.6)	4(50.0)	8(50.0)	3(25.0)
Prohibition on illegal poaching	9(24.3)	6(28.6)	22(51.2)	2(25.0)	6(37.5)	7(58.3)
Lack of firewood	3(8.1)	4(19.0)	7(16.3)	2(25.0)	2(12.5)	2(16.7)
How often do you intrude into the protected						
Often	15(13.9)	2(50.0)	7(7.9)	6(15.0)	2(2.8)	1(2.5)
Sometimes	8(7.4)	6(15.0)	2(2.2)	3(7.5)	7(9.9)	5(12.5)
Once in a while	18(16.7)	12(30.)	12(13.5)	8(20.0)	13(18.3)	8(20.8)
Never	67(62.0)	20(50.0)	68(76.4)	23(57.5)	49(69.0)	26(65.0)

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2: Level Awareness on Wildlife Conservation Practise and on the Host Communities

ANOVA					
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	44.883	4	11.221	3.887	.004
Residual	1105.663	383	2.887		
Total	1150.546	387			

Dependent Variable: The host communities

Coefficients					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	

Awareness on conservation effort being made to protect wildlife	0.577	.229	.142	2.522	.012
Awareness on the existence of national park in this community	0.470	.177	.137	2.657	.008
Awareness on any government policy or law for wildlife conservation in the national park	0.620	.204	.153	3.034	.003
Awareness on any guideline or rules given by NPSON on how to conserve wildlife	-0.462	.222	-.116	-2.077	.038
a. Dependent Variable: the host communities					

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Challenges of the Conservation Practices on the Host Communities based on each Range of Old Oyo National Park

Findings showed that more than half of the respondent from all the six ranges in the study area indicated agreed for Prohibition/restriction to hunting area, reduction of land for farming activities, land for physical development is reduced due to park conserved areas, animal constantly escapes to the village from the park area and animal from the park destroys their farmland as the part of the challenges of the conservation practice communities. Similarly, in terms of restriction this study agreed with the findings carried out by Osunsina & Fagbeyiro (2015) examined local community perception

and attitude towards the non-utilization of natural resources in Old-Oyo National Park, Oyo State, Nigeria. The study was conducted in Old Oyo National Park, Oyo State to assess the local community perception and reaction to the non-utilization of natural resources. The result shows that some of the respondents (41.5 %) agreed that the rules and regulations of the park were strict. Majority of the respondents strongly disagreed to the non-utilization of natural resources in Old Oyo National Park. By restricting access to these park resources, the people feel denied and as such majority (54.3 %) of the respondents are non-compliant to the rules and regulations of the park.

Also, the hypothesis was tested using simple linear multiple regression as shown in Table 4 that [B=0.676, t=-5.520 and P=0.003], Poor implementation of (SZCP) policy [B= -0.441, t= -2.260 and P=0.038], Inconsistency of the donors/partners [B= 0.652, t= 3.821 and P=0.003], Inadequate environmental education [B= -2.017, t= -2.440 and P=0.027], Lack of involvement of the host community [B= -0.227, t= -8.858 and P=0.014], Bush burning/fire outbreak [B= -0.211 t= -19.062 and P=0.001] and Firewood /domestic fuel [B= -0.298, t=5.348 and P=0.025] have a significant effect on the wildlife conservation at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 3: Challenges of the Conservation Practices on the Host Communities based on each Range of Old Oyo National Park

Variable	Tede Range (n=108) F(%)	Oyo-Ile Range (n=40) F(%)	Sepete ri Range (n=89) F (%)	Margu ba Range (n=40) F (%)	Yemes o Range (n=71) F (%)	Tesi Range (n=40) F (%)
Prohibition/restriction to hunting area						
Agree	79(73.1)	36(90.0)	81(91.0)	31(77.5)	47(66.2)	26(65.0)
Undecided	10(9.3)	2(75.0)	1(1.1)	6(15.0)	6(8.5)	1(2.5)
Strongly disagree	19(17.6)	2(5.0)	3(7.5)	3(7.5)	18(25.4)	13(32.5)
Prohibition on certain animal hunting						
Agree	75(69.4)	36(90.0)	84(94.4)	29(72.5)	47(66.2)	28(70.0)
Undecided	7(6.5)	2(5.0)	2(2.2)	3(7.5)	4(5.6)	1(2.5)

Disagree 26(24.1) 2(50.0) 3(3.4) 8(20.0) 20(28.2) 11(27.5)
)

Reduction of land for farming activities

Agree 75(69.4) 35(87.5) 83(93.3) 31(77.5) 52(73.2) 27(67.5)
))

Undecided 11(10.2) 3(7.5) 1(1.1) 1(2.5) 6(8.5) 1(2.5)

Disagree 22(20.4) 2(5.0) 5(5.6) 8(20.0) 13(18.3) 12(30.0)
)

Land for physical development is reduced due to park conserved areas

Agree 71(65.7) 35(87.5) 84(94.4) 26(65.0) 50(70.4) 28(70.0)
))

Undecided 12(42.9) 3(7.5) 1(1.1) 4(10.0) 6(8.5) 2(5.0)

Disagree 25(23.1) 2(5.0) 4(4.5) 10(25.0) 5(21.1) 10(25.0)
)

Animal constantly escapes to the village from the park area

Agree 72(66.7) 33(82.5) 83(94.3) 28(70.0) 48(67.6) 26(66.7)
)))

Undecided 15(13.9) 4(10.0) 2(2.3) 7(17.5) 4(5.6) 1(2.6)

Disagree 21(19.4) 3(7.5) 3(3.4) 5(12.5) 19(26.8) 12(30.8)
))

Animal from the park destroys our farmland

Agree 74(68.5) 34(85.0) 85(95.5) 30(75.0) 51(71.8) 28(70.0)
))

Undecided 7(6.5) 3(7.5) 1(1.1) 0(0) 5(7.0) 1(2.5)

Disagree 27(25.0) 3(7.5) 3(3.4) 10(25.0) 15(21.1) 11(27.5)

Source: Field Survey 2023

Table 4: Challenges Facing the Support Zone Community Programme and the Effect on Wildlife Conservation

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	22.882	7	3.269	13.974	.000 ^b
Residual	3.743	16	0.234		

Total 26.655 23
Dependent Variable: wildlife conservation

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	
Insufficient funds	.676	.122	.628	5.520	.003
Poor implementation of (SZCP) policy	-.441	.195	-.343	-2.260	.038
Inconsistency of the donors/partners	.652	.020	.638	3.821	.001
Inadequate environmental education	-2.017	.827	-1.746	-2.440	.027
Lack of involvement of the host community	-.227	.012	-.277	-8.858	.014
Bush burning/fire outbreak	-.211	.011	-.277	-19.062	.001
Firewood /domestic fuel	.298	.012	.375	5.348	.025

a. Dependent Variable: wildlife conservation

Source: Field Survey 2023

Nigerian-South Africa on Wildlife Conservation Towards Tourism Development in Nigeria: Institutional Interventions

Findings indicated that South-Africa intervention in the tourism sector has influenced socio-economic development of the country in terms of job creations. Apparently, this intervention in tourism sectors significantly enhanced South-Africa GDP and improved the

implementation of the country's national tourism sector strategy:

Tourism contributes over 9% to the South African GDP and supports more than 1.4 million jobs (10% of the workforce), which is why priorities from the National Development Plan have been implemented in the National Tourism Sector Strategy (NTSS) (South African Tourism, 2015; World Travel & Tourism Council, 2015B).

More importantly the findings showed that South-African government ensure the implementation of public private partnership in park reserve. These interventions are largely to grant long-term concessions to host communities for purpose of developing businesses inside the protected area:

The Madikwe initiative has been innovative in negotiating an agreement with provincial Parks Board to grant long-term concessions (essentially user rights) to the villages surrounding Madikwe for the purposes of developing tourism businesses inside the reserve. The initial lodges represent a model 'in which South Africa's current emphasis on cultural and wildlife tourism as strategic industries are fused into community-owned enterprises that maximize jobs, wages, lease fees and other forms of tangible benefit to poor, rural communities' (Koch & Massyn, 2003, p. 30).

This is further corroborated by Smith (2023), findings that South-African adopted several initiatives, one of which is to ensure wildlife conservation in the host communities through tourist and tourism operators initiative as whistleblower:

illegal entries into protected areas and illicit activities (driving on beaches, disembarking from vehicles in game parks etc.), were cured which may have been because field rangers (law enforcement officers) were still active in protected areas as an essential service. Similarly, law enforcement also relies on tourists and tourism operators as "whistleblowers" for many

infringements that occur within the Protected Area Network (Smith, 2023, p. 610).

However, information dissemination, through conferences and workshops for the tourism stakeholders were used by South African government as a tool to enhance tourism in the country. These information disseminations initiatives are done yearly in line with the vision of World Tourism Day:

One of South Africa's most used instruments is information and every year, in the context of the World Tourism Day on the 27th September, they arrange conferences and workshops for all stakeholders in the industry whether they be private, NGOs, governmental departments or funding institutions (Pedersen, 2016: p.18).

Conclusion

The paper indicated that level of awareness of wildlife practices among host communities in Old Oyo National, Nigeria is relatively low but there are some communities that showed level of consideration for wildlife practices in the study area. The study identified some other challenges facing the host communities in Old Oyo National Park is due to the conservation practice which include Prohibition/restriction to hunting area, reduction of land for farming activities, land for physical development is reduced due to park conserved areas, animal constantly escapes to the village from the park area and animal from the park destroys their farmland.

More importantly, the findings indicated that insufficient fund as one of the major challenges facing the wildlife conservation /support zone

community programme in all the six ranges while other challenges such as poaching, poor implementation of SZCP policy illegal lumbering, inadequate environmental education lack of involvement of the host community, the need of pasture for animal and bush burning/fire outbreak are facing the wildlife conservation /support zone community programme which is differs from one range to another. Consequently, challenges facing the support zone community programme has significant effect on wildlife conservation and some of the personnel in Nigeria were not adequately familiar with Nigerian wildlife conservation laws. However, it was affirmed that Nigerian-South Africa intervention is yet to be operational in wildlife conservation due largely to laxity of Nigerian government to adopt the approaches ad the initiatives engaged by the South-African counterpart. The study concluded that there is apt need for sustainable collaboration between Nigeria and South Africa towards capacity building and knowledge sharing on wildlife conservation, which will be of immense contributions to tourism development in Africa.

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